

Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization study of selected volatile organic compounds (VOC's) by Ion Mobility Spectrometry coupled with orthogonal accelerated Time Of Flight Mass Spectrometry

¹Bartosz Michalczuk, ¹Ladislav Moravský, ¹Jana Hrdá and ^{1,2}Štefan Matejčík

¹Comenius University in Bratislava, Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics, Department of Experimental Physics, Mlynská dolina F2 842 48, Bratislava, Slovakia

²National Research Nuclear University MEPhI, Kashirskoe Sh 31, Moscow 115409, Russia

Abstract

In this work we present an Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionisation (APCI) study of several organic solvents (methanol, ethanol, propan-2-ol, acetone, ethyl acetate, diethylamine) using the Ion Mobility Spectrometry (IMS) combined with the orthogonal acceleration Time Of Flight Mass Spectrometry (IMS-*oa*TOF MS). The ions were formed in interactions of the Reactant Ions ($RI - H^+ \cdot (H_2O)_{3,4}$) with the studied volatile organic compounds (VOC's). The ions were analysed by IMS and in by IMS-*oa*TOF to assign ions according to their m/z to the ion mobility peaks. IMS spectra of methanol, ethanol, propan-2-ol and diethylamine exhibited only one peak (reduced ion mobilities of 2.19, 2.07, 1.98, 2.06 $cm^2 \cdot s^{-1} \cdot V^{-1}$ respectively) whereas acetone and ethyl acetate were characterised by two peaks (2.15, 1.85 and 1.94, 1.53 $cm^2 \cdot s^{-1} \cdot V^{-1}$ respectively). The IMS-*oa*TOF spectrometry assigned IMS peaks of VOC's to $MH^+(H_2O)_n$; $n=0,1, 2$ or M_2H^+ ions, where M represent the solvent molecule.

Introduction

The VOC's are widely used in the chemical synthesis and chemical industry. In the analytical chemistry VOC's solvents are used in the processes of sample preparation and in different chromatographic techniques. The traces of the VOC's are very often present in the environment and in the analytical samples. In the case of hyphenated techniques, e.g., thin layer chromatography (TLC) with IMS (TLC-IMS) we deal with the problem of presence of the VOC's contaminants in the IMS spectra. For this reason, we have carried out a study focused on the identification of the VOC's present in the TLC samples. In addition, we have tried to understand the processes of the formation of the VOC's originating ions in IMS as they may interact with the analytes and influence the response of the system^{1,2,3}. In present study we have selected six VOC's – solvents (methanol, ethanol, propan-2-ol, acetone, diethyl amine and ethyl acetate) and we have recorded their IMS spectra in positive polarity Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionisation Ion Mobility Spectrometry (APCI-IMS) and by the Ion Mobility Spectrometry-orthogonal acceleration Time Of Flight Mass Spectrometry technique (IMS – *oa*-TOF MS).

To the selected solvents belong monohydric alcohols - methanol, ethanol, propan-2-ol, which are widely used not only as a solvent but also in other applications, e.g., as a fuel additives (methanol, ethanol) or substrates for the synthesis of other compounds (methanol is used to produce formaldehyde)^{2,4,5,6}. Alcohols due to their ubiquity, were investigated by IMS with many different ionization sources i.e. UV, ⁶³Ni or corona discharge. Depending on concentration one or two peaks were observed corresponding to monomer and dimer formation. From available literature ions like $M \cdot H^+ \cdot (H_2O)_m$ or $M_2 \cdot H^+ \cdot (H_2O)_m$ were form in reaction region of IMS^{7,8,9}.

Another important and widespread solvent is the Acetone, also known as 2-propanone or dimethyl ketone with chemical formula CH_3COCH_3 . It is volatile flammable, colourless compound miscible in water. Acetone is mainly used as a solvent and as an intermediate in many syntheses of organic compounds^{1,10}. Regarding to acetone's high volatility and high proton affinity it is possible to detect it at very low concentration. In most cases even trace

level in range of ppb is enough to detect acetone by IMS. Vautz et al. has observed in positive polarity and radioactive ion source two peaks in IMS spectrum and assigned them to MH^+ and M_2H^{+11} .

Amines are a widespread contaminant in the environment due to their industrial applications or their use as intermediates in chemical and pharmaceutical syntheses^{12,13,14}. The amines are unique as they can form several types of isomers: linear, positional isomers, primary, secondary, and tertiary amines, branched, and cyclic structures and finally, also aromatic isomers¹⁵. Due to their odorous and toxic characteristics these compounds have received much attention as environment pollutants. Some of them are sensitizers and irritants to the skin, mucous membrane and respiratory tract¹⁶. The most frequently used techniques for the determination of amines in air and liquid samples are gas chromatography (GC) coupled with different detectors, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)^{17, 18} ion chromatography¹⁹, spectrophotometry²⁰ and capillary electrophoresis²¹. In some cases, for detection of amines in gas and liquid phase ion mobility spectrometry (IMS) has been used²². Due to their high proton affinities, amines protonate readily in the IMS source, and there is usually little doubt about the site of protonation, as the nitrogen electron lone pair is the favoured site. In most cases the major ionic product is the protonated molecule, although in some cases protonated dimers or molecular or fragment ions are also formed¹⁴.

One of the most important amine is a secondary amine named diethyl amine - (DEA) (Chemical formula - $C_4H_{11}N$) which is strong base compound miscible with most solvents. It is used as an anti-corrosion agent, as well as in rubber, synthetic resin, paint and drug manufacturing, but is useable to produce certain agrochemicals, such as rice herbicides or insecticides pharmaceuticals, radical scavengers and insect repellents²³. In some cases, DEA is frequently use as a chemical reducer^{24,25}.

Ethyl acetate is the organic compound (Chemical formula $C_4H_8O_2$) synthesized in industry from ethanol and acetic acid. It is widely used as a solvent in the production of pharmaceuticals, essential ingredients in many products and materials, in variety of coating formulations such as epoxies, urethanes, cellulosic, acrylics and vinyls, fragrances in food production and precursors of important chemicals being favoured because of its low cost, low toxicity and agreeable odour²⁶. In high purity, it can be used as a viscosity reducer for resins used in photoresist formulations in the electronics industry. Ethyl acetate is rarely selected as a reaction due to its tendency to hydrolysis and transesterification^{27,28}. Mixtures containing ethyl acetate are commonly used in column-liquid chromatography and extractions. Because of its high polarity index (4.4) ethyl acetate can be used very frequently as a polar-solvent to run TLC (Thin Layer Chromatography)^{29,30,31,32,33}.

Experiment

In this study we used a homebuilt Ion Mobility Spectrometry-orthogonal acceleration Time Of Flight Mass Spectrometry (IMS-oaTOF) setup which was already described in detail elsewhere³⁴. It was operated at 370 K and at sub atmospheric pressure (700 mbar). The samples were ionised by Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionisation, using Corona Discharge (CD) in needle to plane geometry as a source of the reactant ions (mainly $H^+(H_2O)_{3,4}$ ³⁵). The needle electrode was manufactured from tungsten wire with diameter of 75 μm , the distance from the plane stainless steel electrode was 5 mm. The CD current was maintained at value of 10 μA . We have used Bradbury-Nielsen type shutter grid with pulse width of 40 μs with frequency of 50 Hz. The IMS device was operated only in positive polarity.

IMS device is coupled with Time Of Flight Mass Spectrometer as it is shown in Figure 1. These two spectrometers can work in three modes: i) IMS ii) MS and iii) IMS-MS when spectrometers are working simultaneously i.e. shutter grid is constantly pulsing and generated ions are separated in the drift tube of IMS and then got to the mass analyser. The ions after passing the

IMS penetrate through 100 μ m pinhole in the ion collector to the first vacuum chamber of the differential pumping system of Time Of Flight analyser. The pressure in the first chamber is about 10⁻¹ mbar while in the flight tube of TOF MS the pressure is about 10⁻⁶ mbar. To achieve this gradient of pressure, differential pumping system was used which consist of three rotary and three turbomolecular pumps, for more details of that pumping system see reference 36. Operating parameters of the experimental setup are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters of the CD-IMS and oaTOF-MS device.

<u>CD-IMS</u>	
IMS drift tube length	11.93 cm
Intensity of electric field	671.8 V.cm⁻¹
IMS operating pressure	700 mbar
IMS operating temperature	370 K
Drift gas flow	500 mL.min⁻¹
Sample flow	10 mL.min⁻¹
CD current	10 μA
Shutter grid pulse width	40 μs
Shutter grid frequency	50 Hz
<u>oaTOF-MS</u>	
TOF pulse width	5 μs
TOF pulse frequency	30.8 kHz
TOF acceleration voltage	2.6 kV
TOF length	54.7 cm

IMS is an analytical method in which the ions are separated in the uniform electric field according to their mobilities. Mobility (K , [cm².s⁻¹.V⁻¹]) is a quantity described by equation (1), where v_d (in m.s⁻¹) represent the drift velocity of ions and E (in V.cm⁻¹) is the strength of the electric field:

$$v_d = K \cdot E \quad (1)$$

The ions traverse the distance from the shutter grid to the detector (drift length d in cm) in time (drift time t_d , in s). The drift time depends on the collisions between the ions and drift gas, which are influenced by their interaction potential, their masses and geometries of the ions. The Eq. (1) can be transformed into:

$$K = \frac{v_d}{E} = \frac{\frac{d}{t_d}}{\frac{V}{d}} = \frac{d^2}{t_d V} \quad (2)$$

Where V is an electric potential difference applied to the drift tube. This formula is used to calculate the mobility of the ions. The ion mobility K depends on the pressure of the drift gas and its temperature, it is more common to present reduced ion mobility (K_0 , [cm².s⁻¹.V⁻¹]) by normalizing the ion mobility to standard conditions of pressure (p , [Torr]) and temperature (T , [K]).

$$K_0 = K \frac{273.15}{T} \frac{p}{760} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1. Schematic view of Ion Mobility Spectrometer coupled with orthogonal accelerated Time Of Flight Mass Spectrometer (IMS-*oa*TOF-MS)³⁹.

Gases and chemicals

We have used dried ambient air prepared by MaSa Tech company air generator as a drift gas in IMS. The air generator includes the moisture traps (Agilent Technologies) and with final water concentration of about 20 ppm³⁵. The gas flow through the drift tube was 500 mL min⁻¹ and the sampling gas flow was set to 10 mL min⁻¹. The drift gas flow was set and controlled by the mass flow meter/controller (Bronkhorst IQ+FLOW series) while sampling gas flow was set using flow meter (PLATON). IMS was operated at sub atmospheric pressure (700 mbar measured Bronkhorst IQ+Flow) to allow suction of the samples at IMS inlet, which substantially simplifies the sampling procedure.

The chemicals used in this study were ordered from Sigma Aldrich or Slavus s.r.o with following purities: For ethyl acetate (Sigma Aldrich) and diethylamine (Sigma Aldrich) purity was stated at 99.8% and 99.5% respectively. Propan-2-ol, methanol and acetone provided by Slavus with 99.5% purity and ethanol also from Slavus with 99.9% purity. Due to high vapour pressures of chemicals dilution of the samples was needed. For this purpose, we have used syringe pump (Kent Scientific, Genie Plus). Glass syringe with volume of 30 mL containing about 0.5 mL of each solvent was interfaced by PEEK capillary with micro splitter connected to the IMS sample inlet. After achieving equilibrium between gas and liquid phase using syringe pump vapours of analyte were injected into sampling gas flow and then introduced into reaction region of IMS. In situation when concentration of analyte in vapours was high enough

to saturate ionisation source, we proceeded with dilution using air from another port of micro splitter.

Results and discussion

The solvents investigated in this paper are widely used in industry and it is obvious that they have already been studied by ion mobility spectrometry^{7, 8, 37, 38, 39}. In Table 2 the values of the values of the reduced ion mobilities obtained in present work are compared with the values available in literature. The present values are in reasonable agreement with the earlier data considering the differences in the experimental conditions like the nature of the drift gas, the drift gas humidity or its temperature.

Table 2. Reduced mobilities K_0 [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$] of IMS peaks and corresponding ions. In brackets values from literature.

Compound	Monomers		Dimers	
	Present values K_0 [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$] Identified ions	Literature K_0 [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$] Identified ions	Present values K_0 [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$] Identified ions	Literature K_0 [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$] Identified ions
Methanol	2.03 $\text{M} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_{1,2} \cdot \text{H}^+$		1.82 $\text{M}_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_{0,1} \cdot \text{H}^+$	1.93 ^{40c}
Ethanol	2.07 $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+ \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_{1,2}$,	2.06 ⁸		
Propan-2-ol	1.98 $\text{M} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_{1,2} \cdot \text{H}^+$,	1.99 ⁸ , 1.98 ³⁸ , 1.97 ^{39b}	1.72 ^a $\text{M}_2 \cdot \text{H}^+$	1.76 ^{39b}
Acetone	2.15 $\text{M} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_{1,2} \cdot \text{H}^+$,	2.19 ⁴¹	1.85 $\text{M}_2 \cdot \text{H}^+$	
Ethyl acetate	1.94 $\text{M} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_{0,1,2} \cdot \text{H}^+$,		1.53 $\text{M}_2 \cdot \text{H}^+$	
Diethylamine	2.06 $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+$, $\text{M} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O}) \cdot \text{H}^+$	2.11 ⁴²	1.46 ^a $\text{M}_2 \cdot \text{H}^+$	

^a dimer peak visible only at very high concentration of analyte.

^b results obtained for nitrogen as a drift gas and with water level below 100 ppt at 317 K.

^c results obtained for nitrogen as a drift gas at 353 K.

The investigated chemicals have proton affinities (PA) (See Table 3) higher than the water molecule. However, only the diethyl amine has PA higher than the proton bond energy of one of the reactant ions $\text{H}^+ \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_{3,4}$ (m/z of 55, respectively 73). The PA has an important impact on the process of ionisation in APCI. The ionisation of analytes in APCI proceeds via following reactions:

The proton transfer reaction (4a) can occur only if PA of the analyte M exceeds the proton bond energy of RI's. In such a case, almost exclusively the protonated ion is formed, which however, can be further hydrated in the drift tube by the reactions (5) and (6). The ions with lower PA (compare to RI) are formed in APCI via switching reaction (4b). These ions are as well subjected in the drift tube to clustering/declustering reaction and the equilibrium distribution of hydrated ions $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+ \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ is established.

The proton affinities of the studied compounds and proton bond energies of RI are listed in the Table 3.

In the case of higher concentration of the VOC's we have observed formation of the dimer ions $M_2 \cdot H^+$ in the reaction chamber. Most probably these ions are formed via ion molecule reactions of the monomer ions:

In the reaction chamber of the IMS spectrometer.

Table 3. Proton affinities (PA) of studied solvents.

Compound	PA [kJ/mol] ^{43, 44}	Proton bond energy [kJ/mol] ⁴⁴
Water	697	
$H^+ \cdot (H_2O)$		726
Methanol	754	
Ethanol	776	
Propan-2-ol	793	
Acetone	812	
$H^+ \cdot (H_2O)_2$		833
Ethyl acetate	836	
$H^+ \cdot (H_2O)_3$		919
Diethylamine	952	
$H^+ \cdot (H_2O)_4$		936

IMS-oaTOF instrument offers the possibility to identify the ions traveling within an IMS peak according to their m/z. All presented IMS and mass spectra (MS) exhibit the IMS peak with $K=2.20 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{V}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ respectively the ions with m/z 55 and 73, which are corresponding to RI $H^+ \cdot (H_2O)_3$ and $H^+ \cdot (H_2O)_4$. These ions are the precursor ions and are responsible for the chemical ionisation of the analytes via reaction (4a) and (4b). MS and IMS spectra of reactant ions are shown in Figure 2. These spectra represent the IMS response of the purified ambient air without any analyte.

Figure 2. Ion mobility (a) and mass (b) spectra for reactant ions (RI).

Figure 3. IMS (a) and MS (b) spectra for methanol at 370 K and 700 mbar. The IMS spectrum was recorded for saturated vapours in order to detect the dimer peak.

The IMS and MS spectra of the methanol are presented in the Figure 3a and b. In the IMS spectrum we have detected monomer peak with the reduced ion mobility $K_0=2.03 \text{ cm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{V}^{-1}$ and dimer peak with $K_0=1.82$. The IMS spectrum has been recorded for saturated vapour

pressure in order to see the dimer peak. This is documented by the corresponding mass spectrum, where a mixture of the RI and the methanol ions is detected. The APCI of methanol resulted in formation of the ion $M \cdot H^+(H_2O)_2$ with m/z 69. We have detected two molecular dimer ions $M_2 \cdot H^+$, $M_2 \cdot (H_2O) \cdot H^+$. Li et al. (Table 2) reported only one value of reduced ion mobility for methanol of $K_0=1.93 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. This value is between the present monomer and dimer value. If we consider that they performed the study in nitrogen drift gas (in contrast to present ambient air), most probably the reported IMS peak corresponds to the dimer ions.

Figure 4. IMS (a) and MS (b) spectra for ethanol at 370 K and 700 mbar.

The spectra of the ethanol (Figure 4a, b) and propan-2-ol (Figure 5a, b) were measured under similar conditions, concentration of 10 ppm. In the IMS spectra besides the RI show one monomer peak with $K_0=2.07 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}\text{V}^{-1}$, $K_0=1.98 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}\text{V}^{-1}$ respectively. These IMS results for alcohols are in agreement with earlier studies of Han et al. and M. Sabo et al.^{8,38,39}. The corresponding mass spectra indicate that in the case of ethanol two ions $M \cdot H^+(H_2O)_{1,2}$ (m/z 65 and 83) are present. Similarly, propan-2-ol formed two monomer ions: $M \cdot H^+(H_2O)_{1,2}$ (m/z 79 and 97). In the mass spectrum of propan-2-ol, in addition to the monomer ions we have detected protonated dimer ions M_2H^+ ($m/z = 121$). The dimer ion was less abundant compare to the monomer ions and that is probably reason why we did not detect it in the IMS spectrum. At elevated concentrations of propan-2-ol the dimer peak has been detected with $K_0= 1.72 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}\text{V}^{-1}$.

Figure 5. IMS (a) and MS (b) spectra for propan-2-ol at 370 K and 700 mbar.

The IMS spectrum of Acetone (Figure 6a) was characterized by two peaks, the first one with K_0 of $2.15 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$ and second one $1.85 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$. The IMS spectrum of acetone is well known^{37,45} and the first peak is associated with the monomer ion and the second one with the dimer. Present IMS-oaTOFMS study confirms this assignment. The acetone monomer IMS peak consist of two ions $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{1,2}$ with m/z 77 and 95. The dimer peak was exclusively formed by protonated dimer ion M_2H^+ (m/z 117).

Figure 6. IMS (a) and MS (b) spectra for acetone at 370 K and 700 mbar and concentration 1 ppm.

In case of ethyl acetate (Figure 7a) IMS spectrum in addition to RI shows two peaks with the reduced ion mobilities of $1.94 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$ and $1.53 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$. The first IMS peak we have assigned to the monomer ion $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+$ (m/z 89) and its water clusters $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{1,2}$ (m/z 107 and 125). The second IMS peak we have related to the molecular dimer and consisted of protonated dimer M_2H^+ ($m/z = 177$) ions. This ion was the dominant peak under present experimental conditions (700 mbar, 370 K and concentration of 1 ppb).

Figure 7. IMS (a) and MS (b) spectra for ethyl acetate at 370 K and 700 mbar.

In the case of more complex IMS spectra we usually apply two dimensional IMS – oaTOF MS spectra, which allow direct assignment between IMS peak and the m/z component in the peak. IMS-MS spectra are obtained in synchronous operation of IMS and TOF-MS. This mode, however, is more time consuming. In Figure 8 we present 2D map of ethyl acetate.

Figure 8. 2D IMS-MS map for ethyl acetate

Horizontal axis in Fig. 8 represent ions time of flight in mass analyser in nanoseconds while vertical axis represents drift time in IMS in milliseconds. In IMS spectrum for ethyl acetate we observe 3 peaks (Fig. 7a), first with reduced ion mobility of $2.19 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$ corresponds to reactant ions $\text{H}^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and $\text{H}^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$. Second peak with $K_0 = 1.94 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$ is related to three ions: $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+$, $\text{M} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O}) \cdot \text{H}^+$ and $\text{M} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{H}^+$ and last peak with $K_0 = 1.53 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$ corresponds to dimer ion M_2H^+ .

The last studied compound was diethylamine. The IMS spectrum (Figure 9a) was dominated by the ion peak with $K_0 = 2.06 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$ at concentration of analyte of 0.1 ppm. The dominant products of diethylamine were identified as $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+$ ion (m/z 74) via reaction 4a and a weak $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (m/z 92) via clustering reactions (5 and 6). Diethylamine has the highest PA of all studied molecules and it was the only compound with PA exceeding that of one RI. This resulted in formation of protonated monomer ion $\text{M} \cdot \text{H}^+$ as a dominant product. At increased concentrations, we were able also detect diethylamine dimer ($K_0 = 1.46 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-1}$) which consists of M_2H^+ (m/z 147) as documented by the mass spectrum.

Figure 9. IMS (a) and MS (b) spectra for diethylamine at 370 K and 700 mbar and concentration 0.1 ppm.

Conclusion:

In this work we have studied formation of positive ions in APCI of selected VOC's using IMS and IMS-oaTOF MS techniques. The IMS technique allows fast and sensitive detection of VOC's and is thus suitable for various analytical applications. However, from IMS spectra alone we are not able to learn about the nature of the ions travelling within IMS peak

(m/z of the ions). The IMS-oaTOF MS technique allows the assignment of IMS peaks to m/z and thus deeper insight in the ion processes between the RI and the VOC's.

The APCI of studied VOC's resulted in formation of monomer and dimer ions. In most cases PA's of molecules were lower than the proton bond energy of RI. In this case the APCI process for monomer included switching reaction resulting in formation of hydronium cluster ions $M \cdot H^+ \cdot (H_2O)_n$ where $n = 1, 2$. Only in the case of diethylamine its PA exceeded the proton bond energy of RI and in this case we have observed as dominant monomer ion the protonated molecular ion $M \cdot H^+$. For several studied molecules, we have detected protonated dimers M_2H^+ , formed, most probably, in ion molecule reaction of the monomer ion with the parent molecule. Presence of protonated dimer ions indicate high proton affinity of the dimer ions.

Acknowledgements:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 674911 and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 692335. This work was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency (APVV-15-0580 and APVV-17-0318) and the Slovak Grant Agency for Science (contract no. VEGA 1/0733/17).

-
- ¹ M. Weber, W. Pompetzki, R. Bonmann, and M. Weber, "Acetone," in Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Ed. Weinheim, Germany: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, 2014, pp. 1–19.
 - ² J. Falbe, H. Bahrman, W. Lipps, D. Mayer, and G. D. Frey, "Alcohols, Aliphatic," in Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Ed. Weinheim, Germany: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, 2013.
 - ³ P. Roose, K. Eller, E. Henkes, R. Rossbacher, and H. Höke, "Amines, Aliphatic," in Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Ed. Weinheim, Germany: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, 2015, pp. 1–55.
 - ⁴ J. Falbe, H. Bahrman, W. Lipps, and D. Mayer, 'Alcohols, Aliphatic', in Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Ed. Weinheim, Germany: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, 2000.
 - ⁵ I. Mellan: Industrial Solvents Handbook, Noyes Data Corp., Park Ridge 1970, p. 123.
 - ⁶ L'osmittel Hoechst, ein Handbuch für Laboratorium und Betrieb, 5th ed., Hoechst, Frankfurt 1974.
 - ⁷ St. Silemann, J. I. Baumbach, H. Schmidt, and P. Pilzecker, 'Detection of alcohols using UV-ion mobility spectrometers', *Analytica Chimica Acta*, vol. 431, no. 2, pp. 293–301, Mar. 2001.
 - ⁸ H. Han et al., 'Determination of alcohol compounds using corona discharge ion mobility spectrometry', *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 751–755, Jan. 2007.
 - ⁹ S. Li, J. Jia, X. Gao, X. He, and J. Li, 'Detection of Toluene, Methanol and Formaldehyde Using Corona Discharge Ion Mobility Spectrometry', *Analytical Letters*, vol. 45, no. 8, pp. 841–849, May 2012.
 - ¹⁰ *Eur. Chem. Week*, September 22, 2008.
 - ¹¹ W. Vautz, L. Schwarz, C. Hariharan, and M. Schilling, 'Ion characterisation by comparison of ion mobility spectrometry and mass spectrometry data', *International Journal for Ion Mobility Spectrometry*, vol. 13, no. 3–4, pp. 121–129, Dec. 2010.
 - ¹² M. Akyüz, "Simultaneous determination of aliphatic and aromatic amines in indoor and outdoor air samples by gas chromatography–mass spectrometry," *Talanta*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 486–492, Jan. 2007.
 - ¹³ B. Sahasrabudhhey, A. Jain, and K. K. Verma, "Determination of ammonia and aliphatic amines in environmental aqueous samples utilizing pre-column derivatization to their phenylthioureas and high performance liquid chromatography," *The Analyst*, vol. 124, no. 7, pp. 1017–1021, 1999.
 - ¹⁴ C. Chen, K. Hou, W. Wang, J. Li, and H. Li, "Ambient temperature nanoelectrospray ion mobility detector for high performance liquid chromatography in determining amines," *Journal of Chromatography A*, vol. 1358, pp. 192–198, Sep. 2014.
 - ¹⁵ Z. Karpas, "Ion mobility spectrometry of aliphatic and aromatic amines," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 61, no. 7, pp. 684–689, Apr. 1989.
 - ¹⁶ N. . Santagati, E. Bousquet, A. Spadaro, and G. Ronsisvalle, "Analysis of aliphatic amines in air samples by HPLC with electrochemical detection," *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 1105–1111, Aug. 2002.

-
- ¹⁷ E. Mazzucco, F. Gosetti, M. Bobba, E. Marengo, E. Robotti, and M. C. Gennaro, "High-Performance Liquid Chromatography–Ultraviolet Detection Method for the Simultaneous Determination of Typical Biogenic Amines and Precursor Amino Acids. Applications in Food Chemistry," *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 127–134, Jan. 2010.
- ¹⁸ I. M. Valente, C. M. Santos, L. M. Gonçalves, J. A. Rodrigues, and A. A. Barros, "Application of gas-diffusion microextraction for high-performance liquid chromatographic analysis of aliphatic amines in fermented beverages," *Analytical Methods*, vol. 4, no. 8, p. 2569, 2012.
- ¹⁹ F. Kvasnička and M. Voldřich, "Determination of biogenic amines by capillary zone electrophoresis with conductometric detection," *Journal of Chromatography A*, vol. 1103, no. 1, pp. 145–149, Jan. 2006.
- ²⁰ Y. Moliner-Martínez, P. Campíns-Falcó, and R. Herráez-Hernández, "A method for the determination of dimethylamine in air by collection on solid support sorbent with subsequent derivatization and spectrophotometric analysis," *Journal of Chromatography A*, vol. 1059, no. 1–2, pp. 17–24, Dec. 2004.
- ²¹ I. Haumann, J. Boden, A. Mainka, and U. Jegle, "Simultaneous determination of inorganic anions and cations by capillary electrophoresis with indirect UV detection," *Journal of Chromatography A*, vol. 895, no. 1–2, pp. 269–277, Oct. 2000.
- ²² S. H. Kim, F. W. Karasek, and S. Rokushika, "Plasma chromatography with ammonium reactant ions," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 152–155, Jan. 1978.
- ²³ Karsten Eller, Erhard Henkes, Roland Rossbacher, Hartmut Höke "Amines, Aliphatic" in *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2005
- ²⁴ Alaa Khedr and Mahmoud Sheha - Quantitative Thin-Layer Chromatographic Method of Analysis of Azithromycin in Pure and Capsule Forms, *Journal of Chromatographic Science*, Vol. 41, January 2003
- ²⁵ Hassan F. Askal, Alaa S. Khedr, Ibrahim A. Darwish, Ramadan M. Mahmoud - Quantitative Thin-Layer Chromatographic Method for Determination of Amantadine Hydrochloride, *Int J Biomed Sci* 2008; 4 (2): 155-160
- ²⁶ A. Szczurek, M. Maciejewska, Ż. Zajiczek, and M. Maziejuk, "Measurement of acetates in air using differential ion mobility spectrometer," *E3S Web of Conferences*, vol. 22, p. 00173, 2017.
- ²⁷ A. Koole, Y. Luo, J. P. Franke, and R. A. de Zeeuw, "Dramatic Signal Reduction in Ion-Mobility Spectrometry by Residues of Solvents," *Journal of Analytical Toxicology*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 191–196, May 1998.
- ²⁸ J. Regueiro, A. Giri, and T. Wenzl, "Optimization of a Differential Ion Mobility Spectrometry–Tandem Mass Spectrometry Method for High-Throughput Analysis of Nicotine and Related Compounds: Application to Electronic Cigarette Refill Liquids," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 88, no. 12, pp. 6500–6508, Jun. 2016.
- ²⁹ C. Wu, W. F. Siems, and H. H. Hill, "Secondary Electrospray Ionization Ion Mobility Spectrometry/Mass Spectrometry of Illicit Drugs," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 72, no. 2, pp. 396–403, Jan. 2000.
- ³⁰ K. Shimada, N. Fukuda, and T. Nakagi, "Studies on Neurosteroids V: Separation and Characterization of Pregnenolone 3-Stearate in Rat Brains Using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography," *Journal of Chromatographic Science*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 71–74, Feb. 1997.
- ³¹ M. R. Menlyadiev, A. Tarassov, A. M. Kielnecker, and G. A. Eiceman, "Tandem differential mobility spectrometry with ion dissociation in air at ambient pressure and temperature," *The Analyst*, vol. 140, no. 9, pp. 2995–3002, 2015.
- ³² M. Tabrizchi, "Temperature Corrections for Ion Mobility Spectrometry," *Applied Spectroscopy*, vol. 55, no. 12, pp. 1653–1659, Dec. 2001.
- ³³ M. Tabrizchi, "Temperature effects on resolution in ion mobility spectrometry," *Talanta*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 65–70, Jan. 2004.
- ³⁴ M. Sabo and Š. Matejčík, "Corona Discharge Ion Mobility Spectrometry with Orthogonal Acceleration Time of Flight Mass Spectrometry for Monitoring of Volatile Organic Compounds," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 84, no. 12, pp. 5327–5334, Jun. 2012.
- ³⁵ B. Michalczyk, L. Moravský, P. Papp, P. Mach, M. Sabo, and Š. Matejčík, 'Isomer and conformer selective atmospheric pressure chemical ionisation of dimethyl phthalate', *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, vol. 21, no. 25, pp. 13679–13685, Jun. 2019.
- ³⁶ M. Sabo et al., "Atmospheric Pressure Corona Discharge Ionisation and Ion Mobility Spectrometry/Mass Spectrometry study of the negative corona discharge in high purity oxygen and oxygen/nitrogen mixtures," *International Journal of Mass Spectrometry*, vol. 293, no. 1–3, pp. 23–27, Jun. 2010.
- ³⁷ M. Tabrizchi, T. Khayamian, and N. Taj, "Design and optimization of a corona discharge ionization source for ion mobility spectrometry," *Review of Scientific Instruments*, vol. 71, no. 6, pp. 2321–2328, Jun. 2000.
- ³⁸ H. Han et al., "Corona Discharge Ion Mobility Spectrometry of Ten Alcohols," *Chinese Journal of Chemical Physics*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 605–610, Dec. 2009.
- ³⁹ M. Sabo and Š. Matejčík, "Corona Discharge Ion Mobility Spectrometry with Orthogonal Acceleration Time of Flight Mass Spectrometry for Monitoring of Volatile Organic Compounds," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 84, no. 12, pp. 5327–5334, Jun. 2012.

-
- ⁴⁰ S. Li, J. Jia, X. Gao, X. He, and J. Li, "Detection of Toluene, Methanol and Formaldehyde Using Corona Discharge Ion Mobility Spectrometry," *Analytical Letters*, vol. 45, no. 8, pp. 841–849, May 2012.
- ⁴¹ C. S. Leasure, M. E. Fleischer, G. K. Anderson, and G. A. Eiceman, "Photoionization in air with ion mobility spectrometry using a hydrogen discharge lamp," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 58, no. 11, pp. 2142–2147, Aug. 1986.
- ⁴² Z. Karpas, "Ion mobility spectrometry of aliphatic and aromatic amines," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 61, no. 7, pp. 684–689, Apr. 1989.
- ⁴³ E. P. L. Hunter and S. G. Lias, 'Evaluated Gas Phase Basicities and Proton Affinities of Molecules: An Update', *Journal of Physical and Chemical Reference Data*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 413–656, May 1998.
- ⁴⁴ H.-P. Cheng, 'Water Clusters: Fascinating Hydrogen-Bonding Networks, Solvation Shell Structures, and Proton Motion', *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A*, vol. 102, no. 31, pp. 6201–6204, Jul. 1998.
- ⁴⁵ J. Puton, M. Nousiainen, and M. Sillanpää, 'Ion mobility spectrometers with doped gases', *Talanta*, vol. 76, no. 5, pp. 978–987, Sep. 2008.